

REACTION OF BENZIL WITH SUBSTITUTED UREA IN PRESENCE OF ALKALI

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The reaction of benzil with substituted urea in presence of alkali has been studied and the compounds isolated have been characterised.

In a previous communication (Sikdar and Ghosh, this *Journal*, 1948, 25, 109) the mechanism of the reaction in which benzil is allowed to react with urea in presence of alkali to yield 5 : 5-diphenylhydantoin has been investigated and outlined. In order to establish such a mechanism it has been considered desirable to extend the reaction with substituted urea derivatives. It has now been found that benzil reacts with monophenylurea in presence of alkali to yield the compounds (I) and (II)

(I)

(II)

The observation, now made with regard to the non-reactivity of symmetrical diphenylurea towards benzil in presence of alkali, confirms the structure (I) of the compound in which the amino group of monophenylurea has reacted with the hydroxy group of benzoic acid. The compound (I) is acidic in nature and is readily soluble in aqueous sodium bicarbonate.

The compound (II), which is insoluble in cold dilute alkali and is readily hydrolysed by alkali to (I), is also obtained by treating (I) with acetic anhydride, and is identical with the compound obtained by fusing monophenylurea with benzoic acid at 180°-190° (Eberly and Dains, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 58, 2546). Eberly and Dains (*loc. cit.*), however, assigned to this compound the structure, 3-phenyl-5 : 5-diphenylhydantoin, which appears to be untenable because such a compound containing -NH-CO- grouping in the ring should be soluble in cold dilute alkali. The analogous thio compound, namely, 3-phenyl-5 : 5-diphenylthiohydantoin (cf. Eberly and Dains, *loc. cit.*) is readily soluble in cold dilute alkali.

When treated with 20% alkali, the compound (I) furnishes a mixture of (III) and a compound to which the structure (IV) is tentatively assigned.

(III)

(IV)

The compound (IV), which is a derivative of 2:5-diketopiperazine and is stable towards hot concentrated hydrochloric acid or 25% alkali, is evidently formed by the hydrolysis of (I) to diphenylamidoacetic acid, $(\text{Ph})_2\text{C} \begin{matrix} \text{NH}_2 \\ \text{CO}_2\text{H} \end{matrix}$, which then forms the cyclic double acid amide (IV) (cf. Kossel, *Ber.*, 1891, 24, 4149). The constitution of (IV) is supported by analytical data, molecular weight determination and also by the fact that the compound yields diacetyl and di-sodium derivatives.

When, however, the compound (I) is treated with 15% hydrochloric acid, a mixture of (II) and (IV) is obtained.

It is now observed that benzoic acid does not react with monophenylurea in presence of alkali, which lends additional support to the mechanism as outlined previously (cf. Sikdar and Ghosh, *loc. cit.*) with regard to the reaction between benzil and urea in presence of alkali to furnish 5:5-diphenylhydantoin.

EXPERIMENTAL

Reaction of Benzil with Monophenylurea in presence of alkali: Formation of Phenylcarbamidodiphenylacetic Acid (I) and 2-Phenylamino-4:4-diphenyl-5-keto-4:5-dihydro-oxazole (II).—(a). Caustic soda (2 g.), dissolved in water (8 c.c.), and alcohol (95%, 6 c.c.) were added to powdered benzil (3 g.). After 15 minutes monophenylurea (3.5 g.) was added and the mixture was allowed to stand at room temperature for 20 hours with occasional stirring. The reaction mixture was diluted with water to 500 c.c., when a solid was precipitated. It was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from alcohol in colorless rectangular plates (II, 0.8 g.), m.p. 203-204°. (Found: N, 8.29. $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2$ requires N, 8.53 per cent). It is insoluble in cold dilute alkali and is dissolved when boiled with 10% caustic soda solution. The alkaline solution, on acidification with concentrated hydrochloric acid, yields a compound confirmed to be identical with (I), described below. This compound (II) has been found to be identical with the one prepared by Eberly and Dains (*loc. cit.*) by fusing monophenylurea with benzoic acid at 180°-190°.

The alkaline filtrate, described above, was acidified with hydrochloric acid, when a precipitate was obtained, which was filtered, washed with water and was crystallised from alcohol in colorless rectangular plates (I, 1.5 g), m.p. 180° (decomp.). It was dried at 100°-110° *in vacuo* and then analysed. (Found: N, 7.88. $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2$ requires N, 8.09 per cent). It is readily soluble in aqueous sodium bicarbonate with effervescence.

(b). When the above reaction mixture, after addition of monophenylurea, was heated under reflux for 2 hours, only the compound (I) was isolated, yield 2.8 g.

Attempt to react Benzil with sym-Diphenylurea in presence of Alkali.—Caustic soda (2 g.), dissolved in water (8 c.c.), and alcohol (95%, 6 c.c.) were added to powdered benzil (3 g.). After 15 minutes, *sym*-diphenylurea (5.5 g.) was added and the mixture was then heated under reflux on the water-bath for 4 hours. The reaction mixture

was cooled and then diluted with water to 250 c.c., when a solid was precipitated which was identified to be *sym*-diphenylurea. From the alkaline filtrate a solid was obtained on acidification, which was identified to be benzilic acid.

No reaction was found to take place even when the mixture was allowed to stand at room temperature for 20 hours without being heated.

Action of Acetic Anhydride on compound (I): Formation of compound (II).—The compound (I, 5 g.) was treated with acetic anhydride (30 c.c.) and fused sodium acetate (5 g.), when considerable heat was developed. The reaction mixture was then heated under reflux for 6 hours, cooled and then poured into cold water with stirring. A semi-solid mass was obtained which gradually solidified. It was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from alcohol (charcoal) in colorless, rectangular plates (1 g.), m.p. 203-204°. Its identity with the compound (II), described previously, was confirmed by mixed m.p. and also by analysis.

Action of Alkali on compound (I): Formation of 1-Phenyl-3-diphenylmethyl-urea (III) and 3:3:6:6-Tetraphenyl-2:5-diketopiperazine (IV).—The compound (I, 3 g.) was heated on the water-bath with aqueous caustic soda (20%, 30 c.c.) for 4 hours. The solution was cooled and diluted with water to 250 c.c., when a solid was precipitated out. It was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from alcohol in colorless rectangular plates (III, 0.7 g.), m.p. 220-22°. (Found: N, 9.05. $C_{20}H_{18}ON_2$ requires N, 9.27 per cent). It is insoluble in dilute hydrochloric acid.

The alkaline filtrate, described above, was acidified with hydrochloric acid, and the solution was concentrated and cooled, when a crystalline solid was obtained which was purified by trituration with aqueous sodium bicarbonate and was recrystallised from dilute alcohol in colorless plates (IV, 0.8 g.), m.p. 242° (decomp.). It was dried at 120°-125° *in vacuo* and then analysed. (Found: C, 80.57; H, 5.68; N, 6.48; M.W., 424. $C_{28}H_{22}O_2N_2$ requires C, 80.38; H, 5.26; N, 6.69 per cent; M.W., 418). It is insoluble in aqueous sodium bicarbonate but readily soluble in cold dilute alkali and precipitated by acids. With caustic soda it gives a di-sodium derivative and the molecular weight has been determined by ascertaining the exact quantity of alkali required to form the di-sodium derivative. An aqueous solution of the substance does not give any distinctive coloration with ferric chloride. It is unaffected by heating with 25% aqueous caustic soda or by prolonged heating with concentrated hydrochloric acid. With acetic anhydride, the substance gives an alkali-insoluble diacetyl derivative, crystallising from alcohol in colorless rectangular plates, m.p. 85-86°. (Found: N, 5.52. $C_{32}H_{26}O_4N_2$ requires N, 5.57 per cent).

Action of Hydrochloric acid on compound (I): Formation of compounds (II) and (IV).—The compound (I, 5 g.) was heated under reflux with 15% hydrochloric acid (75 c.c.) for 6 hours. The mixture was cooled and the insoluble solid was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from alcohol in colorless rectangular plates (2 g.), m.p. 203-204°. Its identity with the compound (II), described previously, was confirmed by mixed m.p., a study of its properties and finally by analysis.

The above acid filtrate was concentrated and then cooled, when a crystalline solid was obtained which was recrystallised from dilute alcohol in colorless plates (1.2 g.), m.p. 242° (decomp.). Its identity with the compound (IV), described previously was confirmed.

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